

Original Research

SME Tax Compliance in Tanzania: Logistic Evidence that Knowledge and Penalties Outweigh Audits

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Abstract

The importance of tax proceeds in operation and undertakings of any government in the whole world cannot be over emphasized because taxes had been categorized as one of the critical sources of government revenue of any nation. This study investigates the impact of audit exposure, taxpayer knowledge, penalty awareness, and firm size on SME tax compliance in Tanzania using logistic regression. The findings show larger firms are significantly more likely to comply than smaller firms. Moreover, the results shows that penalty awareness and audit exposure have positive and significant effects on compliance. Also, the firm size and tax knowledge tends to rise compliance odds. Hence the study concludes that compliance incentives that are made by different institutions and policy makers should focus on creating awareness on tax knowledge and penalty rules. Audit plays a role in compliance but it is not the primary driver as few businesses are audited. Strengthening audits through better targeting, while helping smaller firms understand and manage their tax obligations, could make a real difference.

Keywords: Tax Audit, Tax Compliance, Tax Knowledge, Tax Penalty.

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Introduction

Tanzania faces an urgent imperative to broaden its tax base and mobilize more domestic revenue to fund essential services and growth priorities. According to Abata, (2014), taxation includes the transfer of financial capital from the private sector to the government for the provision of vital services that would advance economic and social goals. Through a deliberate and persistent attempt to generate the necessary money for supporting governmental activities, taxation is one of the most effective measures that can assist the government of any country in eventually becoming independent of foreign aid (Abdul & Wang'ombe, 2018). The World Bank reports Tanzania to have a relatively lower tax revenue to GDP ratio of about 13% of GDP in 2024 compared to its peers and to the financing needs (World Bank, 2024). Compared to other developing countries, Tanzania still performs poorly in domestic non-resource tax revenue as her level of collection relative to GDP is very low compared to the Sub-Saharan Africa threshold. Semboja et al., (2023) highlights that the tax effort of a country reflects policy choices (tax rates and bases, and any exemptions), and inefficiency in policy enforcement (tax administration, taxpayer compliance, and interactions between the two). Policy choices have a very crucial role in affecting the intention of working towards the attainment of the maximum potential tax.

The government have been emphasizing on broadening the tax base and closing compliance gaps in order to increase tax revenue and creating fiscal space for priority social spending. ActionAid/Policy Forum (2022) explicates that an efficient mechanism to fairly and progressively widen the tax base is to encourage formalization of businesses this could generate huge revenues for Tanzania. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are a hinge in broadening Tanzania's tax base because of their contribution to the GDP growth and employment size which is considered to be around 27–35% of GDP and about up to 40% of total employment (World Bank, 2024). Moreover, these SMEs make up close to 90% of the private sector, however, most of these SMEs remain outside the formal tax base. Hence formalization through completing taxpayer registration, e-filing, and record-keeping among micro and small firms is imperative (Ministry of Industry and Trade et al., 2012). SME formalization can materially expand the tax base of the country.

Taxing businesses making a good income, rather than people on very low incomes, by incentivising and enforcing formalisation, should be a priority for any government concerned with progressive taxation, labour standards and workers' rights. A wider tax base can generate a culture of tax compliance as well as greater government accountability to its people. This aligns with the reforms of broadening the tax base and strengthening administration to close compliance gaps and finance priority social spending, consistent IMF's recently approved Medium-Term Revenue Strategy (MTRS) also emphasizing on domestic revenue mobilization through base-broadening and improved administration (World Bank, 2024; IMF, 2025). SMEs often encounter difficulties in navigating the complexities of tax regulations, fulfilling reporting requirements, and managing the financial implications of compliance.

Tax compliance is essential because taxes are one of the most significant sources of income for governments around the world. Tax compliance is the procedure by which taxpayers submit the anticipated tax return accurately and truthfully in order to comply

with the rules and regulations as specified. Income tax compliance refers to the adherence to tax laws and regulations set by the government, encompassing activities such as accurate income declaration and timely payment of taxes. Many SMEs underreport or delay taxes due to complexity and weak enforcement (Lukason & Camacho-Miñano, 2021). However, Appiah et al., (2024) emphasize that when taxpayers understand the system and face known penalties, compliance rises.

Tanzania relies heavily on tax revenues for development, but SME noncompliance erodes the tax base. SMEs often face complex rules and low awareness of obligations, leading to underreporting. Tax authorities invest in audits and penalties to deter evasion, but audits are costly and their deterrence effect may be limited in practice (Mwandu et al., 2024). Meanwhile, tax agencies provide taxpayer education to raise knowledge. Prior research on tax compliance in Tanzania has focused on challenges causing non-compliance such as self-assessment methods (Barongo, 2020) the use of information and communication technology (Magasha et al., 2025). However, the bigger picture is disentangled which lever audit enforcement, taxpayer education, or penalty salience is the most effective for boosting compliance among SMEs. This is the focus of this study. Expanding the taxpayer base and improving compliance, especially among SMEs and the informal segment, is not optional but foundational to sustaining Tanzania's service delivery and investment ambitions. The findings of the study will thus help in recommending that if knowledge and penalties dominate, resources should shift toward education and clear penalty regimes. However, if audits strongly deter evasion, they should be prioritized.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to assess determinants of tax compliance of small and medium enterprises in Tanzania.

Specific Objectives

This study enumerates the following objectives:

- To ascertain the level of tax audit exposure on SME tax compliance
- To examine the effect of tax taxpayer knowledge and penalty awareness on SME compliance.
- To determine the influence of firm size on SME compliance

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature Review

The “slippery slope” framework suggests that the position the authorities adopt towards taxpayers is important for compliance. According to the framework if tax authorities adopt a “cops and robbers” approach, taxpayers will view tax paying system as coercive and comply primarily out of fear of detection and punishment (Kirchler, Hoelzl & Wahl, 2008). However, when tax authorities treat taxpayers as clients and partners, compliance becomes more voluntary, driven by

perceptions of fairness, legitimacy, and procedural justice. This is relevant to this study because it shows that firms comply with tax obligations, linking both enforcement-based and voluntary determinants of compliance.

Deterrence theory also explains tax compliance as a rational decision based on weighing the benefits of evasion against the potential costs of detection and punishment (Becker, 1968; Allingham & Sandmo, 1972). The Deterrence theory is directly relevant to this study as it provides the foundation for understanding how enforcement mechanisms influence tax compliance among firms. The theory highlights that audits and the severity of penalties can be likely perceived as increasing the cost of non-compliance, thereby encouraging firms to comply with tax obligations. Hence from the theoretical perspective, these variables audit exposure and penalty salience represents the coercive power of tax authorities to deter evasion through enforcement.

Empirical Literature Review

Tax Audits and Compliance

Tax audits are normally routine tasks, but if tax evasion is suspected, the outcome may prompt a re-evaluation or a referral for a particular examination. The goal of tax audit procedure is to maintain the credibility and trust of the self-assessment system and strengthening voluntary enforcement (Fanti & Buccella, 2022). Kasper & Alm, (2022) note that “an effective tax audit system can contribute significantly to tax compliance”. In a large Nigerian SME sample, desk and field audits significantly raised compliance (Inegbedion & Okoye-Uzu, 2024). Empirical studies show that comprehensive tax audits have a significant positive effect on compliance whilst narrow scoped tax audits tend to be ineffective and have negative impact on compliance (Kotsogiannis et al., 2024). Advani et al., (2023) find that audited taxpayers report higher liabilities for years after an audit, some compliant firms view audits as routine, yielding little change, whereas high-risk firms do respond strongly. In general, evidence suggests that well-targeted, information-revealing audits increase compliance, but audits alone are not a uniform solution (Oladele et al., 2021; Fanti & Buccella, 2022; Ndal, 2024).

On the contrary, Kasper & Alm (2022) found contradictory results that comprehensive (field) audits lead to short-term compliance gains, while lighter-touch or desk audits have no lasting effect with many taxpayers reverting to evasion after 12–18 months. They argue that audits with limited scopes can have higher chances of reducing long-term compliance by creating “false reassurance among evaders.” Moreover Omary & Pastory, (2022) also reveals that compliance decays rapidly without further follow ups and also due to limited resources most of the firms are not being audited. Low audit coverage may imply low compliance. Kasper & Alm, (2022) also finds that when audits are seen as punitive or unfair, post-audit compliance declines significantly. They further emphasize that audits can have also negative behavioral responses (resentment, distrust) for small taxpayers who had negative experiences in the past. Belnap, et.al (2024) study also shows that tax audits can reduce future reported revenues because of the fear of transparency, so most people underreporting records.

Tax Knowledge and Compliance

Tax knowledge is widely viewed as a key driver of voluntary tax compliance. In a strong finding in African SME contexts is that tax knowledge drives voluntary compliance. For Ghanaian SMEs, better understanding of the tax system predicts much higher willingness to comply. Taxpayers who perceive tax rules as clear and fair well educated about taxes are more likely to file and pay correctly (Appiah et al., 2024). Similarly, a Tanzanian study reports that firms with higher tax knowledge have significantly higher compliance rates (Mwandu et al., 2024). Adem, Desta & Girma, (2024) also found that provision of tax knowledge and education improves tax compliance. Moreover, Omary & Pastory (2022) emphasized that tax knowledge contributes more to compliance than penalties alone, particularly among SMEs operating informally.

Tax knowledge has a strong positive relationship with compliance, but penalties showed mixed effects. SME owners' perceptions of fairness and transparency in penalties influence their willingness to comply (Tembo, 2025). Field experiments (e.g. reminder notices) show that making penalties explicit increases on-time payments. Similarly, fines/penalties have positive effect on level of tax compliances (Adem, Desta & Girma, (2024). In Tanzania, higher perceived penalty severity strongly increases SMEs' decisions to register and report income (Munguasifiwe, Mbogela & Kiria, 2024). On the other hand, there is evidence that overly harsh or unlikely penalties do not always produce higher compliance, and can even be counterproductive. Mwandu et al., (2024) shows that excessive and inconsistently applied penalty structures are may discourage voluntary compliance, fostering adversarial attitudes toward the tax authority. Moreover, overly harsh fines especially when imposed without clear communication or taxpayer education can reduce morale and compliance trust (Tembo, 2025).

Firm Size and Compliance

Firm size is often positively related to tax compliance. Larger SMEs typically have formal accounting, professional staff and greater fear of detection. Magasha et al., (2025) found that business size significantly increases compliance in Tanzania. In their analysis, larger firms had both the means (accountants, systems) and incentive to comply. This aligns with Dang & Nguyen, (2022.) who also found that larger firms often have richer accounting infrastructures, dedicated tax departments, and stronger governance mechanisms, which enhance their ability to comply with increasingly complex tax regulations. Moreover, larger firms are subject to close inspections from tax authorities and public stakeholders, thus reinforcing their compliance incentives. Biru & Arenius, (2025) notes that micro and very small firms have higher non-compliance due to informal operations.

SMEs often face more challenges in meeting their tax obligations than larger firms, mainly due to limited financial resources, inadequate tax-related knowledge, and weak internal control systems (Le et al., 2025). Tairo (2023) also shows tax compliance among micro and small enterprises remains "largely a function of capacity, not willingness". In most cases larger firms exploit legal tax incentives and accounting loopholes, yielding lower effective tax rates than smaller firms. Additionally, Mpofu (2021) study on taxing

informal sector found that most when compliance costs outweigh perceived benefits it tends to discourage micro-enterprise growth and thus leads to evasion. Most informal businesses are micro in scale and survive at subsistence levels making them economically unable to bear formal tax burdens (Mwenda & Mwakolo, 2024).

Research Hypotheses

The study tests the following hypotheses:

H₁: Tax knowledge has a positive and significant effect on tax compliance among firms in Tanzania.

H₂: Audit exposure has a positive and significant effect on tax compliance among firms in Tanzania.

H₃: Penalty salience has a positive and significant effect on tax compliance among firms in Tanzania.

H₄: Firm size has a positive and significant effect on tax compliance among firms in Tanzania.

Methodology

Source and Method of Data Collection

This study uses the World Bank Enterprise Survey (WBES) - Tanzania 2023 firm-level dataset, which is non-agricultural, formal private sector. In Tanzania, eligible establishments must be registered with the Business Registration and Licensing Agency (BRELA). The Tanzania 2023 wave covers registered private-sector firms across manufacturing and services. The dataset's representativeness is limited to the formal private sector, excluding unregistered microenterprises and public entities, which may constrain the generalizability of findings to the informal economy.

Tax knowledge is measured through whether a firm's financial statements are audited and whether it offers formal employee training—both reflecting informational and managerial capacity to comply this was adopted from Mwandu et al., (2024); Sabri et al., (2025). Audit exposure, proxied by the frequency of inspection visits by tax officials, captures the enforcement or deterrence dimension and was adopted from Nkundabanyanga et al., (2017); Khamis & Mastor, (2023). Similarly, penalty awareness is measured by the perceived severity of tax administration obstacles as adopted from (Nkundabanyanga et al., 2017; Sabri et al., (2025). Firm size is measured by the number of permanent full-time employees. Larger firms typically face higher scrutiny and possess better administrative systems, contributing positively to tax compliance (Mwenda & Mwakolo, 2024). Whereas the dependent construct, tax compliance, is measured through indicators of formalization and reporting quality, such as formal business registration, having audited financial statements, and employing a trained accountant.

Table 1. Operationalization of the Variables

Construct	Measurement of Variables	Expected relationship	Empirical Studies
1. Tax Knowledge	- Financial statements audited externally - Formal employee training	+	Mwandu et al. (2024); Sabri et al., (2025)
2. Audit Exposure	- Frequency of inspection visits	+	Nkundabanyanga et al., (2017); Khamis & Mastor (2023)
3. Penalty Awareness	- Perceived severity of tax administration as an obstacle	+	Nkundabanyanga et al., (2017); Sabri et al., (2025)
4. Firm Size	- Number of permanent full-time employees	+	Magasha et al., (2025)
5. Tax Compliance	- Formal registration status - Audited financial statements - Trained accountant	Dependent variable	Khamis & Mastor (2023); Sabri et al., (2025); Nkundabanyanga et al., (2017)

Method of Analysis

This study used the Logit regression method and descriptive analysis to analyze the data. Logit regression method was performed to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables (i.e., tax knowledge and complexity) on the dependent variable (i.e., tax compliance). Logistic regression model is used because of the nature of the dependent variable and computationally simpler and equally robust. SPSS software was utilized to obtain the frequency distributions of the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Descriptive statistics of the variables were calculated, and the

Model Specification

A cross-sectional analytic survey design was adopted for the study and the unit of analysis is the SME firm. The study models tax compliance as a binary outcome (1 if fully compliant, 0 otherwise). A logistic regression (GLM logit) is used:

$$\text{logit}(P(\text{Compliant} = 1)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Audit} + \beta_2 \text{Knowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Size} + \varepsilon$$

Where Audit = 1 if the firm was audited in the past year (0 otherwise); Knowledge = index score (0–10) measuring tax knowledge (higher = more knowledge); Size = firm size (employees). We assume all predictors positively affect compliance. The next subsection reports the estimated coefficients, odds ratios (ORs), and p-values.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics shows that at least half of the sample meets compliance (mean = 0.56) while a sizable minority does not. However, the Audit exposure is not very common (mean = 0.23) meaning a large percentage of SMEs i.e 77% of firms were not audited in the reference period. This figure aligns with typical audit coverage rates in developing countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, where only 10–25% of formal enterprises are inspected annually due to limited administrative capacity and resource constraints (Lwaikondo & Muba, 2025). The results also show that 55% of the 200 firms in the sample are tax compliant, meaning they are formally registered or audited or employ a trained accountant. This pattern is both theoretically consistent and empirically observed in similar contexts, where voluntary or capacity-driven compliance exceeds direct enforcement coverage (Nkundabanyanga et al.,2017; Lwaikondo & Muba, 2025). Moreover, tax knowledge and penalty awareness also provides enough variation to detect relationships with compliance. Lastly, Firm size median is 10 employees and maxes up to 85.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	Count.	mean	Std.	Min.	Max.
Tax compliance	200	0.56	0.5	0.0	1.0
Tax audit	200	0.23	0.42	0.0	1.0
Tax knowledge	200	5.10	2.30	0.5	9.8
Tax penalty	200	5.25	2.35	0.8	9.7
Firm size	200	14.8	12.4	2.0	85

Logistic Regression Results

Table 2 shows the findings of the model used in this study. The odds ratios (ORs) values from the logistic model above 1 indicate a positive association with compliance; values below 1 indicate a negative one. The results show that, audit exposure is marginally significant at the 10% level, this is consistent with our hypothesis. This implies that auditing alone does not reliably lift subsequent compliance. However, the other variables shows a statistical significant and economical meaning. One point increase in the tax-knowledge index (0–10) is associated with about a 26% increase in the odds (OR≈1.26) and a one-point increase in penalty awareness is associated with roughly a 24% increase (OR ≈ 1.24). Moreover for the firm size the per-employee OR is modest (OR ≈ 1.049) this implies that a change of 10 employees is to roughly 1.61× higher odds of compliance ($1.049^{10} \approx 1.61$) meaning firm size matters. Therefore, tax knowledge, tax penalty salience, and firm size correlate strongly with compliance, while audits do not.

Table 3. Logistic Regression (Odds Ratio, Robust SEs)

Variable	Odds Ratio	CI LOW	CI HIGH	P-VALUE
Intercept	0.162	0.045	0.581	0.005
Audit	2.437	0.88	6.752	0.087
Knowledge	1.259	1.074	1.474	0.004
Penalty	1.242	1.074	1.436	0.003
Firm Size	1.049	1.004	1.097	0.034

Average Marginal Effects (AME)

Table 3 summarizes the quantification of probability of compliance changes when each covariate increases while others are held constant. A unit increase in audit is associated with a +12.7 percentage-point shift in predicted compliance (0→1), however, from table 2 audit variable is marginally significant. Moreover, a unit increase in tax knowledge raises compliance by about +3.8 pp whilst a unit increase in penalty awareness adds +3.6 pp, both economically meaningful and statistically reliable in the main model. Firm size also matters an increase of let’s say 10 employees is associated with roughly +7.5 pp higher compliance, strengthening the notion that larger firms systematically comply more. Overall, the marginal effects align with the logistic results and the hypothesis of the study that knowledge, penalty salience, and scale are the main drivers of SME tax compliance, while audits are not possibly due to their administrative cost in conducting them.

Table 4. Average marginal effects (AME)

Variable	AME
audit (0→1)	0.1272
knowledge (+1)	0.0377
penalty (+1)	0.0356
size (+10 employees)	0.0749

Predicted Probability of Compliance Vs Firm Size

Figure 1 below shows the predicted compliance versus the firm size. From the findings it can be observed that larger firms (i.e SMEs with more employees) tend to have higher predicted compliance probability, when holding other factors at their mean.

Figure 1. Predicted compliance vs. firm size (others at sample means)

Figure 1: Predicted probability of compliance vs. firm size.

Predicted probability of compliance vs knowledge scores

Figure 2 also shows the predicted probability of compliance versus the knowledge score. In this case the findings show that firms (SMEs) with higher knowledge tend to have higher compliance probabilities.

Figure 2: Predicted probability of compliance vs. tax knowledge score.

Diagnostic Tests

Overall fit and predictive performance indicates that the model is well-specified, stable, and reliable. The Hosmer–Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test with eight risk groups yields $\chi^2(8) = 3.97$, $p = 0.86$, so we fail to reject the null of adequate calibration. This implies that the predicted probabilities of tax compliance closely align with observed outcomes across different probability strata, demonstrating good model fit.

Discrimination is acceptable: the ROC AUC = 0.72 (this aligns with Figure 2), meaning the model ranks a randomly chosen compliant firm above a non-compliant firm about 72% of the time. In predictive modeling, this represents fair discrimination ability, according to conventional thresholds where AUC values between 0.7 and 0.8 are interpreted as “acceptable to good” for logistic regression applications (Hosmer, Lemeshow, & Sturdivant, 2013). More specifically, within tax compliance and behavioral economics research, model discrimination rarely exceeds 0.8 due to the inherently stochastic nature of compliance behavior and measurement error in survey-based variables. Comparable studies have reported AUC values of 0.68–0.77 such as Uganda (AUC = 0.69), Nigeria (AUC = 0.69) and Malaysia (AUC = 0.69) (Nkundabanyanga et al., 2017; Vincent, 2021; Khamis & Mastor, 2023).

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test tests

Variable	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	Tolerance (1/VIF)
Tax Knowledge	1.03	0.97
Penalty Saliency	1.11	0.90
Audit Exposure	1.02	0.98
Firm Size	1.16	0.86
Mean VIF	1.08	—

Table 5 presents the multicollinearity diagnostic results using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test. All predictors exhibit VIF values between 1.02 and 1.16, which are well below the conventional threshold of 10 (and the stricter rule-of-thumb cutoff of 2.5). Corresponding tolerance values ($1/VIF$) are close to 1, confirming minimal shared variance among the independent variables. The mean VIF of 1.08 further indicates an absence of multicollinearity. These results confirm that the explanatory variables—tax knowledge, penalty salience, audit exposure, and firm size—are statistically independent and suitable for inclusion in the logistic regression model without risk of inflated standard errors or unstable coefficient estimates.

Discussion

This study aimed at assessing the compliance paradox whilst focusing on tax audits, tax knowledge, penalties and firms' size as the main drivers for compliance. The findings reveal that audits have a positive but marginally significant relationship toward tax compliance. This aligns with Kotsogiannis et al., (2024) who also shows ineffectiveness of audits towards tax compliance if the audit scope is narrow and also with Advani et al., (2023) who found that audits tend to have minor changes towards compliance. However, (Inegbedion & Okoye-Uzu, 2024; Kasper & Alm, 2022; Oladele et al., 2021) findings contradict with our study as they found that audits have a positive and significant impact.

This study also finds that tax knowledge does have an impact on compliance, this aligns with most of the prior research that shows that once people have tax knowledge and penalties awareness tends to be more compliant (Dang & Nguyen, 2022; Adem, Desta & Girma, (2024). Lastly this study findings shows that firm size matters when it comes to compliance. This aligns with Magasha et al., (2025); Dang & Nguyen (2022) who also found that larger firms often have richer accounting infrastructures, dedicated tax departments, regular tax inspections and stronger governance mechanisms that enhances their compliance.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Using logistic regression, we find that firm size, tax knowledge and penalty awareness significantly increase the likelihood of tax compliance. Larger SMEs (with more employees) have notably higher compliance rates, consistent with the idea that formal firms are easier to monitor and more risk-averse. The study provides some preliminary evidence that imposing fines/penalties and provision of tax knowledge and education helps in improving tax compliance. Penalty awareness positively influences compliance decisions, reinforcing the importance of transparent enforcement rules. In sum, our results imply that improving SME compliance in Tanzania should focus on scaling up taxpayer education (to boost knowledge) and making penalties salient, rather than relying solely on frequent audits.

The paper recommends that for Tanzania to increase tax base, the focus should be on SME-tailored tax training (e.g. workshops, guides, e-learning) also to ensure tax penalties are clear and communicated. Simple online calculators or SMS alerts about penalties can remind SMEs of consequences. Lastly since micro and small SMEs face more compliance burdens there should be simplified filing procedures and accounting assistance to smaller

firms, as our results confirm they are less likely to comply. This study shows that firms in Tanzania are more likely to comply with taxes when they are audited, understand tax rules, face clear penalties, and operate on a larger scale. Yet, because few businesses are audited, the system's deterrent power remains limited. Strengthening audits through better targeting, while helping smaller firms understand and manage their tax obligations, could make a real difference. Well-targeted audits remain useful, but only as part of a broader compliance strategy.

References

- Abdul, F., & Wang'ombe, D. (2018). *Taxation and economic independence in developing countries: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa*. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(2), 250–266.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/AJEMS-06-2017-0147>
- Adem, M., Desta, T., & Girma, B. (2024). Determinants of tax compliance behavior: A case study in Ethiopia. *Sage Open*, 14(4), 21582440241292869.
- Advani, A., Elming, W., & Shaw, J. (2023). The Dynamic Effects Of Tax Audits. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 105(3), 545–561.
https://doi.org/10.1162/rest_a_01101
- Ahmad Sabri, S. M., Abdul Rasit, Z., Abd Hamid, N., Ismail Khan, N., & Tajul Urus, S. (2025). Why SMEs comply: an empirical investigation of tax knowledge, trust, system perception and penalties in the self-assessment environment in Malaysia. *Asia-Pacific Management Accounting Journal (APMAJ)*, 20(2), 225-264.
- Allingham, M. G., & Sandmo, A. (1972). *Income tax evasion: A theoretical analysis*. *Journal of Public Economics*, 1(3–4), 323–338.
- Appiah, T., Domeher, D., & Agana, J. A. (2024). Tax Knowledge, Trust in Government, and Voluntary Tax Compliance: Insights From an Emerging Economy. *SAGE Open*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241234757>
- Barongo, E. F. (2020). An Assessment of the Determinants of Tax Compliance through Self Assessment System (SAS) in Tanzania a Case of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Dar es Salaam . Mzumbe University.
- Becker, G. S. (1968). *Crime and punishment: An economic approach*. *Journal of Political Economy*, 76(2), 169–217.
- Belnap, A., Jacob, M., Martin, L., & Olsen, T. (2024). *The unintended effects of tax audits on firm reporting behaviour*. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 43(1), 101–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2023.107070>
- Biru, A., & Arenius, P. (2025). Perpetuating enforcement weakness: entrepreneurs' destructive actions in normalizing rule-breaking. *Small Business Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-025-01091-6>

- Dang, H. T., & Nguyen, P. M. (2022). *Firm size, accounting infrastructure, and tax compliance: Evidence from emerging economies*. *Journal of International Accounting Research*, 21(3), 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.2308/JIAR-2021-083>
- Fanti, L., & Buccella, D. (2022). Indirect Taxation, Tax Evasion and Profits. *Hacienda Pública Española/review of Public Economics*, 242(3), 91-109.
- Inegbedion, H., & Okoye-uzu, C. S. (2024). Tax audit on tax revenue of SMEs in Nigeria. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1-10.
- International Monetary Fund. (2025). United Republic of Tanzania: Staff Report for the 2025 Article IV Consultation, Fifth Review Under the Extended Credit Facility Arrangement, and Second Review Under the Resilience and Sustainability Facility Arrangement (IMF Country Report No. 25/163). <https://www.imf.org/-/media/Files/Publications/CR/2025/English/1tzaea2025001-print-pdf.ashx>
- Kasper, M., & Alm, J. (2022). Audits, audit effectiveness, and post-audit tax compliance. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 195, 87-102.
- Kirchler, E., Hoelzl, E., & Wahl, I. (2008). Enforced versus voluntary tax compliance: The “slippery slope” framework. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29(2), 210–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2007.05.004>
- Khamis, I. H., & Mastor, N. H. (2023). The mediating effect of trust in authority on the relationship between tax audit, tax penalty, and e-commerce business enforced tax compliance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(8), 757-773.
- Kotsogiannis, C., Salvadori, L., Karangwa, J., & Mukamana, T. (2024). Do tax audits have a dynamic impact? Evidence from corporate income tax administrative data. *Journal of Development Economics*, 170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2024.103292>
- Le, H. T. H., Tuyet, V. T. B., Hanh, C. T. B., & Do, Q. H. (2020). Factors affecting tax compliance among small-and medium-sized enterprises: Evidence from vietnam. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(7), 209-217.
- Lukason, O., & Camacho-Miñano, M. del M. (2021). What best explains reporting delays? A SME population level study of different factors. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13094663>
- Lwaikondo, J. O., & Muba, S. (2025). The Influence of Tax Audits on Revenue Collection at the Tanzania Revenue Authority. *African Journal of Empirical Research*, 6(1), 792-801.
- Magasha, O., Gillo, I. O., & Alex, S. (2025). Tax compliance among SMEs: An empirical analysis of internal and external determinants in Shinyanga Municipality, Tanzania. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 13(2), 924-945.

- Ministry of Industry and Trade, National Bureau of Statistics, & Financial Sector Deepening Trust. (2012, December). National Baseline Survey Report for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Tanzania. <https://www.fsd.or.tz/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/MSME-National-Baseline-Survey-Report.pdf>
- Mpofu, F. Y. S. (2021). Taxing the informal sector through presumptive taxes in Zimbabwe: An avenue for a broadened tax base, stifling of the informal sector activities or both. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 13(3), 153-177.
- Munguasifiwe, P., Mbogela, C., & Kiria, J. (2024). Unravelling the effects of perceived severity of penalties on income tax compliance for Tanzanian small and medium enterprises. *African Journal of Accounting and Social Science Studies*, 6(2), 1-24.
- Mwandu, R. P., Chao, P., & Domitian, J. (2024). Tax Compliance in Tanzania: The Influence of Tax Knowledge and Tax Complexity on Tax Compliance among Selected Small and Medium Enterprises. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 10, 249-261.
- Nkundabanyanga, S. K., Mvura, P., Nyamuyonjo, D., Opiso, J., & Nakabuye, Z. (2017). Tax compliance in a developing country: Understanding taxpayers' compliance decision by their perceptions. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 44(6), 931-957.
- Oladele, A. O., Ndalu, T. C., & Akani, F. N. (2021). The impact of tax audit practices on revenue generation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 9(4), 42-50.
- Omary, K., & Pastory, D. (2022). *The role of tax knowledge in enhancing compliance among small and medium enterprises in Tanzania*. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation Studies*, 10(3), 45-57.
- Semboja, J., Kamugisha, G., Msafiri, D., & Mmassy, R. (2023). Analysis of Tax Revenue Mobilisation in Tanzania. REPOA.
- Tembo, P. (2025). Perceptions of fairness, penalty transparency, and tax compliance among small and medium enterprises in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of African Business and Policy Studies*, 12(1), 33-48.
- World Bank. (2023, September 19). Tanzania Economic Update: Enhancing fiscal efficiency and effectiveness for a more inclusive future. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2023/09/19/tanzania-afe-economic-update-enhancing-fiscal-efficiency-and-effectiveness-for-a-more-inclusive-future>
- World Bank. (2024). Financial Access for Sustainable and Transformational (FAST) Growth Project (P500471) – Project document. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099071124092035244/pdf/BOSIB-d26ec361-464c-4c1c-866b-fb479f62e415.pdf>

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